

Single-molecule investigation of the binding interface stability of SARS-CoV-2 variants with ACE2.

Ankita Ray,¹ Tran Thi Minh Thu,^{2,3} Rodrigo A. Moreira,⁴ Rita dos Santos Natividade,¹ Danahe Mohammed,^{1, #} Melanie Koehler,^{1, ##} Joshua D. Simpson,¹ Simon J. L Petitjean,¹ Qingrong Zhang,¹ Laurent Gillet,⁵ Adolfo Poma,^{6*} David Alsteens^{1,7*}

¹ Louvain Institute of Biomolecular Science and Technology, Université catholique de Louvain, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium

² Faculty of Materials Science and Technology, University of Science—VNU HCM, 227 Nguyen Van Cu Street, District 5, Ho Chi Minh City 700000, Vietnam

³ Vietnam National University, Ho Chi Minh City 700000, Vietnam

⁴ Basque Center for Applied Mathematics, Mazarredo 14, 48009 Bilbao, Bizkaia, Spain

⁵

⁶ Institute of Fundamental Technological Research, Polish Academy of Sciences, Pawińskiego 5B, 02-106, Warsaw, Poland

⁷ Walloon Excellence in Life sciences and Biotechnology (WELBIO), 1300 Wavre, Belgium

PRESENT ADDRESS:

Mechanobiology and Soft Matter Group, Interfaces and Complex Fluids Laboratory, Research Institute for Biosciences, University of Mons, Mons, Belgium

Leibniz Institute for Food Systems Biology, Technical University of Munich, Freising, Germany.

KEYWORDS: SARS-CoV-2, ACE2, RBD, Variant, Omicron, Delta, Mu, force, AFM, atomic force microscopy, Contact map analysis, free energy, Jarzynski equality, energy, structure, neutralization, biolayer interferometry, BLI, convalescent patient, sera, antibody.

ABSTRACT

The novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 has caused a global pandemic, and much research is being done to understand the virus and find ways to combat it. One important aspect of this research is the study of the binding interface between the virus and human receptors. This interface plays a crucial role in virus transmission and is a potential target for therapeutic intervention. In this study, the binding interface between the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of SARS-CoV-2 and the ACE2 receptors was investigated using atomic force microscopy and steered molecular dynamics. The aim was to understand the impact of variants of concern on the binding affinity between RBD and ACE2. Results showed that some of the latest variants have a stronger binding affinity, leading to the possibility of immune escape. The findings of this study provide important insights into the dynamics of the RBD-ACE2 interaction and can inform the development of new strategies for combating SARS-CoV-2. This research highlights the importance of continued monitoring and study of the virus and its variants to effectively control its spread and minimize its impact on public health.

INTRODUCTION

The first outbreak of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) in 2003 and the more recent outbreak of SARS coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) show very different patterns of virus spread around the world. While the former remained highly localized, SARS-CoV-2 resulted in a global pandemic. Soon, the Wuhan strain began to evolve into numerous variants of concern (VOCs), demonstrating how easily this virus can accommodate antigenic changes in its spike glycoprotein (S) without any loss of fitness.¹⁻³ Although these mutations were anticipated, the first VOCs to emerge possessed primarily mutations in the binding interface between the S glycoprotein and the angiotensin-converting enzyme2 (ACE2) receptor. The main effect of these mutations was to increase the stability of the binding complex.^{4,5} However, rapidly, with the appearance of the first people immune to the virus through previous contact with it, and also with the appearance of the first vaccines, the virus came under pressure and began to select mutations that allowed it to escape host immunity.⁵⁻⁷

In this regard, some mutations in SARS-CoV-2 have been shown to be responsible for large conformational changes such as the D614G, present in all VOCs, which facilitates the transition from the closed to the open state prior to ACE2 binding⁸⁻¹¹ Others mutations localized in the receptor-binding motif (RBM) influence the stability with ACE2 receptor and do affect the efficiency of monoclonal antibody (mAb) neutralization.^{12,13} The RBM, which is part of the receptor-binding domain (RBD) is a prime target for neutralizing antibodies that are induced by infection or by currently used COVID-19 vaccines¹⁴ and is very tolerant to mutations (**Figure 1A**). N501Y, for example, present in all VOCs except Delta, is thought to increase ACE2 binding,¹⁵ while the E484K mutation in Beta and Gamma VOCs lead to the inefficacy of previously developed monoclonal antibodies approved as treatment for COVID-19. In this regard, although the Omicron BA.1 variants have 15 point mutations in RBD, with some that would appear to be deleterious to the stability of the complex with ACE2.^{16,17}

Current knowledge, despite all the enormous efforts, threatens to be outdated if not anticipating future evolutions, therefore a better understanding on the impact of spike protein mutations on the spike-receptor interaction at atomic resolution is of pivotal importance as well as its influence on its inhibition by antibodies and immune response. In this context, atomic force microscopy (AFM) has proven to be useful technique enabling to the interaction forces between the SARS-CoV-2 S-glycoprotein and the ACE2 receptors on model surfaces and on living cells.¹⁸ In addition, previous AFM experiments in combination with molecular dynamics (MD) simulation enabled to map the binding interaction between the S-glycoprotein of various VoCs and ACE2 receptors, enhancing our biophysical understanding of the key role played by the mutations in stabilizing the binding interface between the S-glycoprotein and the ACE2 receptor.^{18,19}

In this study, we exploited the power of single molecule force spectroscopy (SMFS), combined with in silico approaches based on SMD simulation and Jarzynski equality to decipher the RBD/ACE2 dissociation process under mechanical loading (Figure 1B, C) of the newer variants of concern. We calculated the mechanical strength, kinetic and thermodynamic parameters describing the binding free-energy landscape of the RBD/ACE2 complex. The molecular mechanisms underlying the formation of the complex in the different mutants was highlighted via the mapping of molecular contacts, thus allowing to highlight an evolution of the binding interface which results in a modification of the stability and the recognition by antibodies, which can lead to an escape of the acquired immunity via a previous infection by an older variant or after vaccination

Figure 1. Single-molecule investigation of SARS-CoV-2 variants using AFM and SMD. (A) Phylogenetic tree of SARS-CoV2 showing the emergence of the variants of concern (VOCs) Omicron, Delta, Mu. (B) Probing of RBD mutants binding to ACE2 receptors using atomic force microscopy (AFM). (C) All-atom steered molecular dynamics (SMD) simulation with tethered ACE2 protein showing effect of force pulling on the RBD protein.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Probing VOCs RBD/ACE2 binding free-energy landscape

In order to study the evolution of the stability of RBD/ACE2 binding interfaces for the most recent VOCs, including the Mu, Delta and Omicron variants, we first force probed the complex by AFM, using the force spectroscopy mode (Figure 2A). To this end, force-distance (FD) curves were recorded to extract and quantify the forces required to rupture those complexes, giving access to their stabilities (Figure 2B). To mimic the cellular surface, model surfaces were prepared by covalently grafting purified human ACE2 receptors via NHS/EDC chemistry on -OH/-COOH terminated alkanethiol surface, as previously established.¹⁸ On the other hand, the various RBD were covalently grafted onto the AFM tips at the end of an heterobifunctional polyethylene glycol spacer, providing sufficient mobility to the RBD to establish a stable complex with the ACE2 molecules. To investigate the kinetics of the RBD/ACE2 complex, force-distance (FD) curves were recorded for the between the ACE2 coated surface

and the AFM tips derivatized with the various VOC RBD. FD curves showing specific single binding events were sorted based on the overall shape of the rupture events. Unbinding events are considered as specific if they (i) significantly detach from the base line noise (at least a threefold difference), (ii) are located at a distance >12nm from the contact point (consistent with the PEG spacer extension) and (iii) are consistent with the extension of a protein-based polymer (can be fitted with the worm-like chain model)²⁰.

This first analysis enabled us to extract the various binding frequencies for the various RBDs (Figure 2C). We observed that the Omicron-RBD shows a significantly higher binding frequency, while the binding frequencies for the Mu and Delta RBDs are similar. To better understand this difference, we decided to investigate the kinetics and thermodynamics of the RBD/ACE2 complex formation. The Bell-Evans model is a biophysical model used to describe the kinetics of a receptor ligand complex^{21,22}, assuming that the bound and unbound state are separated by a single-energy barrier located at a distance x_u (corresponding to the distance to the transition state) from the bound state. The height of this barrier influences the association rate (k_{on}) and dissociation rate (k_{off}). The overall binding affinity can be described by the equilibrium dissociation constant (K_d), which is equal to the ratio of k_{off} to k_{on} . Experimentally, the k_{off} can be estimated by probing the binding strength of a molecular complex under increasingly applied loads. Practically, the AFM tip is retracted at different speed (100-20,000 nm/second) resulting in various loading rate (LR). The rupture forces are then plotted against the loading rate on a semi-log graph scale, also called dynamic force spectroscopy (DFS) plots (Figure 2D-E).

Overall, we observed that for the three VOCs, the RBD-ACE2 complexes withstood forces in the range of 20 to 500 pN over the explored range of LRs (Figure 2D-E). We can also observe that the distribution of rupture forces is very wide even for close LRs, which suggests that under our experimental conditions we probe both single and multiple bonds. Since the Bell-Evans model predicts that the rupture force of a bond is directly proportional to the logarithm of the LR, those forces must be analyzed for small ranges of LR. Therefore, bond strengths were sorted for smaller LR ranges and displayed as histograms (Figures S1-S3). These histograms show multiple peaks, confirming the presence of both single bond ruptures but also the simultaneous breakage of multiple bonds. The various histograms were fitted with multiple Gaussian fits, enabling us to extract the mean rupture force for the single bond rupture. These mean values are then overlaid on the respective DFS plots, and fitted with a linear regression. Based on the Bell-Evans model, the x_u and k_{off} parameters, describing the energy landscape of the probed molecular complex, are then extracted from the slope and the intercept of the fit extrapolated to zero force, respectively.

Based on this analysis, we obtained x_u of 0.90 ± 0.01 nm (mean \pm S.D.) for both the Omicron and Mu RBDs and a slightly higher value of 1.10 ± 0.02 nm for the Delta RBD (Figure 2D-F). While the value for the Dela is similar to the value we previously

observed for the RBD^{WT}/ACE2 interface, the lower value observed for the latest variants could suggest a higher rigidity of the binding interface.

Next, by assuming that the RBD-ACE2 complex formation can be approximated by a pseudo-first-order kinetics, the k_{on} was extracted from the binding frequency (BF) measured at various contact times (Figure 2D-F, insets). The contact time refers to the duration when the tip and surface are in contact. This association rate depends on the effective concentration C_{eff} , described as the number of binding partners (RBD protein+ACE2 receptor) within an effective volume V_{eff} accessible under free-equilibrium conditions. We approximated V_{eff} by a half-sphere with a radius including the linker, RBD protein, and ACE2 receptor.^{18,19,23} For the three different interacting biomolecular pairs, we saw an increase in the binding frequencies as a function of the contact time. The extracted k_{on} are in the same order of magnitude as those observed for the RBD^{WT} as well as early VOCs.¹⁹

From the k_{off} and k_{on} , the dissociation constant K_D of the complexes were calculated and revealed similar affinities of the Mu and Delta variants, with K_D of 386 ± 63 nM (mean \pm S.D.) and 360 ± 117 nM, respectively. For the Omicron the affinity is slightly enhanced to 258 ± 43 nM. Those K_D values correspond to high-affinity interactions, confirming the high-stability of the complexes established by the VOCs and the cognate ACE2 receptor.

Figure 2. Probing the binding free-energy landscape of the RBD/ACE2 complexes by AFM. (A) . The AFM tip probes the interaction during the pixel-by-pixel scanning of the sample and extracts for each pixel a so-called force-distance (FD) curve obtained by making cycles of approach and retraction. **(B)** Bell-Evans model describing a ligand-receptor bond as a simple two-state model. The bound state is separated from the unbound state by a single

energy barrier located at distance x_u . Lowering of the activation energy upon application of an external force ($F>0$) is shown as red dotted lines. k_{off} and k_{on} represent the dissociation and association rate, respectively **(C)** Box-whiskers plot of the binding frequencies (BF) measured by AFM between the functionalized tip (RBD mutants) and the grafted ACE2 model surface. **(D-F)** Dynamic force spectroscopy (DFS) plot showing the individual force extracted from individual FD curves (gray data points) as well as the mean rupture forces, determined at various loading rate (LR) ranges measured either between ACE2 receptor and Mu-RBD **(b)**, $N=1094$ data points), Delta-RBD **(c)**, $N=1541$ data points), Omicron-RBD **(d)**, $N=1434$ data points). Data corresponding to single interactions were fitted with the Bell-Evans (BE) model (straight line), providing average k_{off} and x_u values. Plots in the inset: The binding frequency (BF), expressed in percentage, is plotted as a function of the contact time.

Towards an atomistic analysis of the stability of the RBD/ACE2 interface.

In order to get insightful information on the molecular mechanisms of the mechanical stability of the VOCs RBD/ACE2 complexes, SMD simulations mimicking the above AFM experiments were performed (See Figure 1C). These simulations provide a detailed view of the unbinding process and allow the extraction of quantitative parameters describing the unbinding process, such as the rupture force, defined as the maximum force (F_{\max}) (pN) reached during the rupture process. Overall, the simulations revealed for the three VOCs a rapid change in the binding interface, which was evaluated for each variant at the rupture force and assessed in terms of the disappearance of protein-protein contacts at the RBD/ACE2 interface. We determined contacts at F_{\max} and searched for those which are vanished after 50 ps, corresponding to a displacement of $\approx 0.5\text{\AA}$ (See Supplementary Movies 1-4). This number was as large as 19 contacts for the Omicron compared to 6 contacts for Mu variant (See Table 1-4).

To highlight those changes, we displayed, for the three VOCs, some snapshots of the initial complex structures (Figure 3A-D), as well as at the rupture of the complexes (Figure 3E-H). It is clear from those structures that the interactions present at the RBD/ACE2 interface, which are very different between variants, influence the observed rupture trajectories, as also shown in Figure 3I-L. To get a quantitative measure over the ensemble of 20 SMD trajectories, we computed the average force ($\langle F_{\max} \rangle$) for all cases and obtained the following values: 531 ± 56 pN (mean \pm S.D.) for the WT, 515 ± 61 pN for Mu, 459 ± 75 pN for Delta, and 544 ± 59 pN for Omicron, that support WT and Omicron variants can accommodate the largest forces over the contact area. To determine the residue-residues interactions involved in the detachment of the RBD from the ACE2 receptor at F_{\max} , we calculated in each trajectory the most stable interface interactions using contact maps (CM) via the OV+rCSU protocol.^{24,25} The consensus interactions are reported in Tables 1-4 for all cases studied. Graphical representations of the most relevant interactions are depicted in Figure 3A-D (green solid lines) and the remaining set after 10 ps is shown in Figure 3E-H.

Contact map analysis also revealed that the Omicron RBD/ACE2 complex variant shows a larger number of stabilizing interactions distributed all over the RBD/ACE2 interface, probably conferring an enhanced nanomechanical stability compared with WT and the two other variants. Indeed, we find that for all complexes, the breakup process starts on the side of the interface located around residue 501 of the RBD, progressively extending along the interface towards the opposite side (See Supplementary Movies 1-4). For the Omicron variant, which has no less than 19 key contacts distributed fairly evenly at this interface, the breakup process is similar to an unzipping mechanism as reported in other protein complexes. For the Mu and Delta variants, which mostly have very stable contacts at the opposite end (around RBD residue 484), the breakup trajectory is steeper than that of Omicron with a two-step breakup process.

Figure 3. SMD simulation of the RBD/ACE2 complex for WT and three main SARS-CoV-2 variants. Panel (A) shows the ribbon-like representation of the protein complex for the WT, panel (B) for Mu, panel (C) for Delta and panel (D) for Omicron. For each variant is indicated by a solid line the position of the mutated residue. In the case of Omicron, the mutations at the RBD/ACE2 interface are highlighted by black beads and the remaining mutations, which are associated with immune evasion, are shown by orange beads. In addition, we display the interface contacts (green solid line) which are responsible for the mechanical stability and offer a resistance to the detachment of the RBD from the tethered ACE2. Middle panel shows snapshots at F_{max} in SMD. Solid green lines represent those contacts still present 10 ps after reaching F_{max} . Bottom panel shows the force-displacement profiles computed by SMD for WT and variants. The initial distance value corresponds to the distance between ASP615 and THR333 in ACE2 and RBD respectively after MD equilibration of the complex. Color data convention follows: black for WT, orange for Mu, blue for Delta and red for Omicron.

Insights into the RBD/ACE2 energetics using *in silico* approach.

Furthermore, we also computed via Jarzynski inequality (see method section) the non-equilibrium free energy $\Delta G_{unbound}$ that is the difference between the G^{TS} at the transition state (TS) and G_{bound} at the bound state. This quantity, although relative and sensitive to several parameters in the SMD protocol such as pulling residue, speed and spring constant, allows us to compare different protein complexes. The $\Delta G_{unbound}$ obtained for the WT and the three VOCs are presented in Figure 4A. First, we can clearly observe that the WT has the highest ΔG_{bu} of ≈ 14.5 kcal/mol, which corresponds to a K_d around 1 nM. We can see a trend in ΔG , that is larger for Omicron than Delta

and Mu variants, which supports the stronger ACE2 recognition by the Omicron variant. The same trend is supported by the work (W) calculation over the whole trajectories. We report the following $\langle W \rangle$ values for each case studies, 153.2 ± 27.2 kcal/mol (WT), 119.6 ± 19.6 kcal/mol (Mu), 118.3 ± 20.5 kcal/mol (Delta) and 174.0 ± 30.0 kcal/mol (Omicron). This quantity shows for the Omicron variant the large work required to separate this variant from the ACE2 receptor. In fact, the work is a more reliable quantity as it depends on the entire process whereas ΔG_{unbind} depends on the determination of the TS and reference bound state.

Moreover, Figure 4B shows the lifetime of the RBD/ACE2 complex under the applied force in SMD simulation, where we show that the Omicron variant reaches the longest time scale among all variants and this is in consistency with larger work required to separate this complex. In fact, our findings highlight the resilience of this complex to withstand large force fluctuations in the range of 400-600 pN (Omicron) forces in our SMD. In particular Omicron is capable of spreading the total force over a larger contact area, as shown in Figure 4C, which affects the ACE2 receptor interaction which is in line with a previously reported study.²⁶ We also noticed a structural perturbation in the ACE2 receptor during SMD simulations, characterized by root mean-square deviation (RMSD) of a protein structure with respect to a target structure which is considered at $t=0$. The RMSD quantifies the dimensional disparity between two structures, and RMSD computed between the reference protein structure and each consecutive trajectory frames in the MD simulation. This is shown in Figure 4D-G which depicts how the force perturbation is propagated in the RMSD of Mu and Omicron variants, reaching ~ 0.4 nm, whereas ACE2 in complex with Delta variant and WT undergoes a smaller perturbation of 0.3nm. This result corroborates the high degree of adhesion of Omicron RBD onto the ACE2 receptor, in practice due to activation of several bonds at the complex interface.

We show in Figure 4H-K, the normalized total number of native contacts ($\#NC = NC(t)/NC(t=0)$, in the range of 0 to 1) in ACE2 during the SMD simulation. A deviation from 1 means internal reorganization in the protein during the application of force in SMD. The observed changes are below $\sim 1\%$ in the number of native contacts (NC) that vanished for Mu and Omicron variants, while for WT and Delta variants the changes are close to initial reference values meaningless in our simulations. In general, these results show small conformational changes in ACE2 and thus its functional activity is preserved during the unbinding process for WT and Delta whereas some minor effects are reported for Mu and Omicron variants.

Figure 4. Energetic and structural characterization of RBD/ACE2 complex by SMD. The binding free energy (ΔG) by Jarzynski equality for each system. (B) Lifetime shows the amount of time in ns the protein complex remains bounded before reaching F_{max} . (C) The interface area computed by <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/pisa/>. Middle panels display the RMSD for all cases. Panel (D) shows RMSD profile for WT, (E) for Mu, (F) for Delta and (G) for Omicron. Bottom panels show the evolution of the total number of contacts during SMD. Color data convention as described in Figure 3.

Table 1: List of the most relevant 11 interface contacts at F_{\max} during SMD for WT. Protein-protein interactions are calculated via OV+rCSU contact map protocol. Distance between two $C\alpha$ forming a contact and type of interaction are also reported.

Residue in ACE2	Residue in RBD	$d(C\alpha-C\alpha)[\text{\AA}]$	Type of interaction
GLN42	GLN498	10.6	Polar
LYS353	TYR505	9.30	
THR27	TYR489	11.04	
HIS34	GLN493	10.75	
GLN42	TYR449	12.75	
ASP355	THR500	8.51	
ARG357	THR500	12.16	
LEU79	PHE486	8.94	Hydrophobic
TYR41	THR500	11.60	
TYR41	GLN498	10.08	
GLN24	ASN487	9.11	Polar

Table 2: List of the most relevant 12 interface contacts at F_{\max} during SMD for Delta variant.

Residue in ACE2	Residue in RBD	$d(C\alpha-C\alpha)[\text{\AA}]$	Type of interaction
GLN24	ASN487	9.88	polar
LYS31	GLN493	11.01	
HIS34	LEU455	10.45	
MET82	PHE486	10.24	Hydrophobic
GLU35	GLN493	10.94	
THR27	TYR473	12.93	
THR27	TYR489	10.67	
LYS31	TYR489	9.98	
LEU45	THR500	10.61	
LEU79	PHE486	8.72	Hydrophobic
THR27	PHE456	13.31	
LYS31	PHE456	9.19	

Table 3: List of the most relevant 6 interface contacts at F_{\max} during SMD for Mu variant.

Residue in ACE2	Residue in RBD	$d(C\alpha-C\alpha)[\text{\AA}]$	Type of interaction
THR27	PHE456	11.71	
GLN42	GLN498	10.93	Polar
LEU79	PHE486	9.63	
LYS353	TYR505	9.56	
THR27	TYR489	10.71	
LYS31	GLN493	11.17	

Table 4: List of the most relevant 19 interface contacts at F_{\max} during SMD for Omicron variant.

Residue in ACE2	Residue in RBD	$d(C\alpha-C\alpha)[\text{\AA}]$	Type of interaction
THR27	TYR473	13.33	
LYS31	PHE456	9.78	
LYS31	TYR489	9.64	
TYR41	THR500	13.27	
LYS353	TYR501	11.78	
SER19	ALA475	8.64	
LYS353	GLY502	6.34	
GLY354	GLY502	4.69	
ARG357	THR500	12.57	
MET82	PHE486	9.51	Hydrophobic
GLY354	HIS505	7.28	
SER19	ASN477	6.51	Polar
THR27	TYR489	10.70	
LEU79	PHE486	8.33	Hydrophobic
SER19	GLY476	8.90	
HIS34	LYS493	11.12	
THR27	PHE456	13.62	
HIS34	LEU455	11.33	

Monitoring immune neutralization of VOCs

RBD domains play a critical role in the early stages of infection, controlling the binding of the virus to its host receptor and its ability to infect. Therefore, it is not surprising that it is the main therapeutic target, via the development of neutralizing monoclonal antibodies (mAbs), nanobodies or via vaccination.^{3,6} To evaluate whether variant could escape to immune neutralization, we tested two IgG1 mAbs (B-K45 and B-R41, Diaclone SAS, France) directed against the WT RBD (Figure 5A). In our previous study, we showed that B-R41 only neutralize the WT and Alpha variant, while B-K45 was still active against the WT, Alpha, Beta, Gamma, and Kappa variants.¹⁹ Therefore, we decided to further investigate the neutralizing capacity of the B-K45 on the Mu, Delta, and Omicron VOCs to determine if they acquired new immune evasion properties. To this end, we measured the BF between the respective RBD and the ACE2 receptor, first in the absence of mAbs and after the injection of B-K45 at increasing concentrations (1, 10, and 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) (Figure 5B). We observed that, even though B-K45 was able to significantly reduced the BF by ~50% for both Delta and Mu variants (IC_{50} at ~10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for Delta and ~50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for the Mu variant), its potential is significantly reduced in comparison with previous VOCs. This is even more clear for the Omicron, for which the B-K45 neutralizing capacity is almost abolished, probably to the high density of mutations at the RBD surface that enhance the number of contact and stabilize the interface. To confirm the specificity of mAb1 blocking, we also performed a control experiment in the presence of isotype mAb (B-D38, Diaclone SAS, France) and found no reduction in BF for all three variants respectively (Figure 5C).

Figure 5. Blocking by monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) and sera from convalescent patients to probe neutralization potential. (A) AFM setup to measure BF of the interaction between ACE2 and the RBD mutants. (B-C) Graph showing blocking potential of mAb 1 and 2 against RBD. Binding probabilities were estimated before and after incubation with mAbs at increasing concentration ($1-50\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in PBS). Data are representative of at least $N=3$ independent experiments (tips and sample) per mAb concentration. P-values were determined by two-sample t-test in Origin. The error bars indicate S.D. of the mean value. (D) Graph showing blocking in the presence of sera 1-2 obtained from convalescent patients and sera 3 obtained from non-vaccinated and non-infected individual. (E-L) Histogram showing distribution of rupture forces for Delta/ACE2 (in blue) and Omicron/ACE2 (in red) interaction in the presence of sera 1-3. (M-R) BiSIF experiment showing the association and dissociation regime of the sensogram for binding of Delta-RBD (in blue, top panel) and Omicron-RBD (in red, top panel) to ACE2 receptors. Middle and lower panel represents the kinetics in the presence of sera 1 and 2 (diluted 1:1000 v/v with 0.1% BSA in PBS).

Studies have reported that, COVID-19 vaccination increases the plasma antibody concentration, with IgG titers increasing 30 times in comparison to non-vaccinated individuals.^{27,28} To study the molecular basis of neutralization in a more physiological context and to evaluate the possible immune escape of the more recent variants, we wanted to study the efficacy of individual sera in blocking the ACE2/RBD interaction. We selected sera from patient who were (i) vaccinated and infected with the Delta variant after vaccination (Sera 1), (ii) non-vaccinated but infected with the Delta variant (Sera 2), (iii) never been in contact with the vaccine or the virus using a serum obtained in 2019 (Sera 3). Using AFM, we tried to evaluate the blocking capacity of

those sera on the interaction established between the ACE2 and the Delta or Omicron RBD. We found that while Sera 1 is able to retain its neutralizing potency against both Omicron and Delta variants as shown in Figure 5C (reduction in BP >50% in both cases), Sera 2 lost its blocking potency. While Sera 1 and 2 were able to neutralize the RBD/ACE2 interface, experiments performed in the presence of Sera 3, which is devoid of specific antibodies showed complete absence of neutralizing activity (Figure 5D). Furthermore, we constructed individual force histograms for the blocking experiment with Sera 1-3 and compared it with the histogram obtained in the absence of antibodies. (Figure 5E-L) (N=1024 data points were used to construct each histogram). We found that Sera 1 and 2 were able to reduce the interaction of spike protein with ACE2 in both cases, and moreover was able to reduce the ability of the RBD to form multivalent bonds as observed by the decrease of binding events in the range of force between 100 and 150 pN, that corresponds to multivalent interactions. In the control serum, the RBD/ACE2 complex formation is not affected, as suggested by a very similar force distribution in the histograms (Figure 5H,L). These results underline the ability of AFM to evaluate the neutralizing power of antibodies, either purified like monoclonal antibodies, or present in more complex media such as sera.

To determine the prophylactic protection against SARS-Cov-2, a highly sensitive screening technique that can monitor the neutralization breadth of antibodies for better therapeutic intervention is needed. In this regard, using biolayer interferometry (BLI) which is a fiber-based biophysical detection technique²⁹ we measured the avidity between ACE2 and RBD in the presence of sera from convalescent patients. BLI is a bulk-technique that measures the kinetics of the associating molecules by monitoring the change in the amplitude and phase of white light that is reflected off the biosensor surface.³⁰ We used Ni-NTA coated biosensor to graft the Delta RBD and amine-reactive biosensors for the Omicron RBD respectively. It was found that both Delta and Omicron have high avidity (K_D ~31 nM for Delta and ~9 nM for Omicron) towards ACE2 receptors (Figure 5 M,P). The overall higher (~30 times) K_D values observed using AFM compared with BLI can be attributed to an overestimation of k_{on} rates during the BLI experiments due to rebinding of protein, which is often a caveat associated with bulk measurements. To test the RBD blocking potential, the BLI experiment was performed in a simple dip-read format, in which the biosensor was loaded first with the antigenic RBD protein, following which they were allowed to interact with the antibodies present in the sera (diluted 1:1000 μ L in 0.1% bovine serum albumin in PBS) to form a primary RBD-antibody complex (Figure 5M, inset). This primary RBD-Ab complex was made to react with the ACE2 receptors at 0.025 mg/ml in PBS, to further evaluate its ability to interfere with ACE2 binding. Since, most antibodies directed against SARS-CoV2 target the spike protein, we observed a positive wavelength shift (given in nm) as a function of time corresponding to the formation of a stable primary RBD-Ab complex. (See Fig S4) In the presence of the intermediate blocking step with Sera 1 and 2, both variants exhibited almost negligible

avidity for the ACE2 receptor in the association phase. (Figure 5 N-O,Q-R) (expansion of the sensogram showing the association and dissociation traces). Taken together, our BLI sensograms highlight the fact that the immune response from individual post vaccination and/or infection lead to the presence of Ab which compete with the first recognition step between the ACE2 receptors and the RBD domain, leading to protection against the virus infection.

CONCLUSION

The Omicron variant was able to evade neutralization almost completely presumably due to the constellation of mutations which confers the ability to escape humoral immunity by an increase in shape complementarity between TYR side chains and a favorable T-shaped π - π stacking interaction.^{5,17,31} Additionally, this effect is further enhanced by the introduction of new salt-bridge interactions which remodels the electrostatic interaction. Due to this antigenic shift, mAbs like sotrovimab and cilgavimab/tixagevimab have reduced potency.^{5,32-34}

Previous studies have shown that individual vaccinated after COVID-19 infection were found to elicit higher neutralization capacity.³⁵

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Functionalization of AFM tips. MSCT-D cantilevers (Bruker) were used to probe the interaction between S1 RBD subunits (Diacclone SAS, 715-H26-0BU, 715-H28-0BU, 715-H25-0BU,) and extracellular domain of purified ACE-2 receptors (Diacclone SAS, 715-H19-0BU). The cantilevers were cleaned by immersing in chloroform for 10 min and further cleaned by UV-radiation and ozone. Silanization was performed under an argon atmosphere by placing the clean AFM tips in a desiccator with separate vials containing 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane APTES (30 μ l) and triethylamine TEA (10 μ l). The tips were left in the desiccator for 2 hours, following which the desiccator was flushed with argon and the tips were left to cure for two days. Heterobifunctional NHS-PEG₂₄-Ph-aldehyde linkers were used to chemically functionalize APTES coated AFM tips as previously described.¹⁹ Briefly, silanized AFM tips were immersed in a solution of NHS-PEG₂₄-Ph-aldehyde (3.3 mg in 0.5 mL of dry chloroform) in the presence of triethylamine (30 μ l). After 2 hours of incubation in the dark at room temperature, the cantilevers were thoroughly washed with chloroform three times and dried under a gentle stream of nitrogen.

For AFM tips functionalized with RBD proteins (Delta and Mu RBD) containing a His-tag, 100 μ l of a 100 μ M tris-nitrilotriacetic amine (tris-NTA) (Toronto Research Chemicals, Canada) was placed on Parafilm, and 2 μ l of freshly prepared sodium cyanoborohydride (NaCNBH₃) solution was added and thoroughly mixed. Tips were incubated at room temperature in the solution for 2h. Then, 5 μ l of 1M ethanolamine solution (pH 8.0) was added and incubated for 10 min. The mixture of 50 μ l of RBD solution (0.1 mg ml⁻¹ in PBS, pH 7.4, and 2.5 μ l of 5 mM NiCl₂) was placed on the cantilevers and incubated for 2h at room temperature. After incubation, they were washed in PBS solution three times to remove non-specifically adsorbed molecules. Subsequently, the AFM tips were washed three times with PBS buffer and stored in filtered PBS for a maximum of two days at 4° C.

For AFM tips functionalized with RBD proteins containing an Fc tag (Omicron RBD), 50 μ L of protein solution (0.1 mg/ml in PBS buffer pH 7.4) was added to the Ald-PEG₂₄-Ph-coated cantilevers placed Parafilm inside a Petridish. To this, sodium cyanoborohydride (NaCNBH₃, 1 μ L of 1 M stock solution) was added and mixed thoroughly. The tips were incubated for 1 hour at room temperature. Then, ethanolamine hydrochloride (2.5 μ L of 1 M stock solution, pH 8.0) was added to block the unreacted aldehyde groups on the AFM cantilever. Subsequently, the AFM tips were washed three times with PBS buffer and stored in filtered PBS for a maximum of two days at 4° C.

Preparation of Au model surfaces grafted with ACE2. Purified hACE-2 protein (Diacclone, SAS, 715-H19-0BU) was immobilized on gold-coated surfaces (Au on polished Si wafers) using NHS-EDC chemistry as previously described. Briefly,

gold-coated surfaces were rinsed with ethanol, dried under nitrogen, cleaned for 15 min in an UV-ozone cleaner and incubated overnight in solution containing alkanethiol (99% 11-mercapto-1-undecanol 1mM (Sigma Aldrich) and 1% 16-mercaptohexadecanoic acid 1mM (Sigma Aldrich) in ethanol). Resultant surfaces were washed with ethanol, dried under a gentle stream of nitrogen, and immersed in a solution 25 mg mL⁻¹ mg of dimethylaminopropyl carbodiimide (EDC) and 10 mg mL⁻¹ of N-hydroxy succinimide (NHS) for 1 hour at room temperature. Finally, the chemically activated samples were incubated with ACE2 protein (25 µL, 0.1 mg mL⁻¹ in PBS, pH 7.4) on parafilm for 1 hour at 4° C and washed with PBS buffer. Functionalized surfaces were used on the same day of the experiment.

FD-based AFM on model surfaces. FD-based AFM on model surfaces was performed at room temperature in PBS using functionalized MSCT-D probes (Bruker, nominal spring constant of 0.030 N/m and actual spring constants measured prior to the experiment using thermal tune method). A Bruker Nano8 operated in force-volume (contact) mode in fluid (Nanoscope software v9.1) was used for the determination of kinetic on-rate (measuring the binding frequency for different contact times of 0, 50, 100, 150, 250, 500, and 1000 ms) at room temperature. For each force map, a scan size of 5µm, a set point force of 500 pN, resolution of 32 × 32 pixels and a line frequency of 1 Hz were used. A JPK Force Robot 300 AFM (JPK, Germany) was used to measure the loading rates and interaction forces by DFS analysis (using a constant approach speed of 1 µm/s and variable retraction speeds of 0.1, 0.2, 1, 5, 10, and 20 µm/s). The relationship between the pulling velocity (*v*) and loading rate (LR) is given as:

$$LR = \frac{\Delta F}{\Delta t} = k_{eff} \cdot v$$

where $\Delta F/\Delta t$ being the applied force over time, and k_{eff} the effective spring constant of the system. To identify peaks corresponding to adhesion events occurring between RBD linked to the PEG spacer and the receptor model surface, the retraction curve before bond rupture was fitted with the worm-like chain model (WLC) for polymer extension. The latter expresses the force-extension (*F*-*x*) relationship for semi-flexible polymers and is described by the following equation, with l_p the persistence length, L_c the contour length and $k_b T$ the thermal energy:

$$F = \frac{k_b T}{l_p} \left(\frac{1}{4 \left(1 - \frac{x}{L_c}\right)^2} + \frac{x}{L_c} - 0.25 \right)$$

DFS data were extracted using the JPK Data Analysis software (JPK) and further analysed using Origin software (OriginLab, version 2019) to fit histograms of rupture force distributions for distinct LR ranges. A nonlinear iterative fitting algorithm (Levenberg-Marquardt) was used with the Bell Evans model to extract kinetic and thermodynamic parameters of the interactions. For kinetic on-rate analysis, the binding probability (fraction of curves showing binding events) was determined at a

certain hold time (t) (the time the tip is in contact with the surface). Those data were fitted and K_D calculated as described previously.

In brief, the relationship between interaction time (τ) and BP is described by the following equation:

$$BP = A \times [1 - \exp\left(\frac{-(t-t_0)}{\tau}\right)]$$

where A is the maximum BP and t_0 the lag time. Origin software is used to fit the data and extract τ . In the next step, k_{on} was calculated by the following equation, with r_{eff} the radius of the sphere, n_b the number of binding partners, and N_A the Avogadro constant

$$k_{on} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot 4\pi r_{eff}^3 \cdot N_A}{3n_b\tau}$$

The effective volume V_{eff} ($4\pi r_{eff}^3$) represents the volume in which the interaction can take place. Least-squares fits of the data to a mono-exponential decay curve (line) provide average kinetic on-rates (k_{on}) of the interaction.

All experiments were reproduced at least three times with independent tips and samples. The error bars indicate S.E. of the mean value.

All-atom MD simulation. The initial structure of the RBD-ACE2 complex was obtained from the PDB file with entry 6M0J which corresponds to wild type (WT) case. Further modeling was carried out to accommodate the mutations in Delta, Mu and Omicron RBD variants. For the case of delta 2 mutations (i.e., L452R and T478K), Mu 3 mutation (i.e., R346K, E484K, N501Y) and Omicron 15 mutations (i.e., G339D, S371L, S373P, S375F, K417N, N440K, G446S, S477N, T478K, E484A, Q493R, G496S, Q498R, N501Y, Y505H, T547K) were modeled and energy minimized by UCSF ChimeraX software.³⁶ The new structures were solvated in a rectangular box with dimensions equal to 14nm x 14nm x 45nm. Our simulation box was composed of about 867000 atoms, which includes 12510 atoms only for RBD-ACE2 complex atoms, about 285000 water molecules. The whole box was neutralized with Na^+ and Cl^- ions. We have employed periodic boundary conditions (PBC) in all three Cartesian coordinates. To perform MD of the whole system, we employed CHARMM36m³⁷ force field for the proteins and TIP3P water model. The leapfrog algorithm³⁸ was used to integrate the equations of motion with a time step of 2 fs. The length of all bonds was constrained by the LINCS algorithm.³⁹ The velocity of atoms was changed periodically by v-rescale temperature coupling which maintained the temperature stable with a relaxation time of 0.1 ps over the whole MD simulation. Short range cutoff radius of 1.4 nm was used to calculate the van der Waals (vdW) and electrostatic forces. To calculate the long-range electrostatic interaction, we employed the particle mesh Ewald (PME) method. The system temperature was maintained at 300K using the V-rescale thermostat

algorithm⁴⁰ and the pressure was kept at 1 bar using the Parrinello-Rahman algorithm.⁴¹ MD simulations were conducted using the GROMACS package, version 2020.4.⁴²

Steered Molecular Dynamics (SMD) simulation. The molecular system was energy minimized by the steepest descent method and equilibrated by performing an NVT simulation for 1 ns and followed by NPT simulation for another 1 ns. These two steps maintained the temperature and pressure at 300 K and 1.0 bar respectively. The last snapshot of the NPT equilibration was chosen as the initial structure for the SMD simulation.

The RBD/ACE2 complexes were placed in a rectangular box that has a size large enough to accommodate the full detachment of the RBD under a pulling force from the anchored ACE2 receptor and also satisfy the minimum image convention condition. An external force was applied to a dummy atom, which is connected with the C α atom of the residue THR-333 in the RBD, through a spring with a stiffness k . The pulling direction was chosen parallel to the longest side of the simulation box. To prevent the ACE2 receptor to be dragged along the pulling direction, the position of C α atom of the residue ASP-615 was restrained.

The force experienced by the pulled atom is $F=k(vt -x)$, where x is its displacement from the initial position and v is a pulling speed. The spring constant k was set to 600 kJ/mol/nm² which is the typical value used in the AFM experiment.⁴³ Like preceding studies^{44,45} in all SMD simulations the pulling speed was chosen to be $v = 10 \text{ \AA/ns}$, which is much higher than typical AFM experimental speed. However, as confirmed by our studies the pulling speed will affect the absolute value of the rupture force and work, but the relative mechanical stability should not depend on v .^{46,47} With this choice of k and v parameters, the mechanical stability of protein systems is in qualitative agreement with experiments on protein-ligand,^{46,47} protein-protein and fibril-like systems.⁴⁵

As shown previously, the rupture force F_{max} can be used to characterize the mechanical stability of the protein complex. In addition, we can use the pulling work (W) to characterize the systems, defined by:

$$W = \int f(x)dx = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (f_{i+1} + f_i)(x_{i+1} - x_i) \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of simulation steps, f_i and x_i are the force experienced by the pulled chain and position at step i . The pulling work W is more robust than F_{max} because the pulling work is a function of the entire process, while the rupture force is determined only in a single state. Moreover, the mechanical stability in terms of the free energy (ΔG) can be obtained using Jarzynski's equality, as was shown by. In this

regard, Hummer and Szabo, by showed that ΔG is related to W by the following equation,

$$\exp\left(\frac{-\Delta G}{k_B T}\right) = \left\langle \exp\left(\frac{W(t) - \frac{1}{2}k(z_t - vt)^2}{k_B T}\right) \right\rangle_N \quad (2)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle_N$ stands for averaging over N trajectories, z_t is the displacement of the pulled atom along the pulling direction and W is given by Eq. (1). We performed 20 independent SMD simulations (i.e., $N=20$). Since z_t is also known from the simulation, then we can calculate $\exp(-[W-k(z_t-vt)^2/2]/k_B T)$ for each trajectory and also then calculate the average over the ensemble of trajectories to get ΔG as a function of time (or the related displacement).

Contact map analysis of the RBD/ACE2 interface of variants. The determination of the most relevant protein-protein interactions at the RBD/ACE2 interface follows our contact map analysis which has been already validated in several protein complexes^{24,48} and also for the study of the SARS-CoV-2 spike glycoprotein [16]. The contact maps are based on the OV+rCSU approach and it has been stored in our server (<http://pomalab.ippt.pan.pl/GoContactMap/>). We obtained from our SMD trajectories 500 contact maps which were sampled every 10 ps of simulation time. Then we perform a detailed analysis of contacts which disappeared between subsequent contact maps. This step allows us to identify the most relevant interactions that lead to F_{\max} . Moreover, when we observe a drop in the forces F and this effect is correlated with sudden loss of contacts, hence the CM highlights the set of relevant contacts which are contributing the most to the force peak for each trajectory. Finally, we construct out of the whole 20 trajectories a set of the most stable interaction which gives stability to the RBD/ACE2 interface during the SMD simulation.

Study participants

Blood samples processing

Antibody inhibition assays. The binding frequency for the interaction between RBD of different mutants and the ACE-2 receptor were measured before and after incubation with different concentrations (1, 10 and 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in PBS) of two different monoclonal antibodies (B-K45 and B-D38-isotype control)(Diaclone SAS, France). Briefly, three force-volume maps were recorded on three different areas as described previously in the absence of any antibody (i.e., force-volume mode, $1\mu\text{m/s}$ approach and retraction speed, map size of $5\mu\text{m}$, threshold force of 500 pN, 32×32 pixels, 512 samples/line,

frequency of 1Hz, and contact time of 250 ms on surface). Thereafter, antibodies were added to the fluid cell and three maps were recorded for each concentration.

Biolayer Interferometry. Affinity between the RBD and ACE2 was measured on a BLI instrument (Octet, ForteBio, Sartorius) device equipped with Ni-NTA biosensors (Sartorius). After hydrating the biosensor for 10 min and performing an initial baseline (1 min), the biosensor surface was loaded by RBD-Delta (0.001 mg/ml in PBS). The Omicron RBD was grafted on an amine-reactive biosensor (Octet, ForteBio, Sartorius) via NHS/EDC coupling step followed by a quenching step with ethanolamine.⁴⁹ Then the biosensor was dipped in a PBS well to collect a second baseline following which it was dipped in a well containing ACE2 (0.025 mg/ml in PBS, 300 s, association phase). Finally, the dissociation was performed in a well with PBS (300s) All measurements were conducted at 25 °C and shaker speed 1000 rpm. The association and dissociation part of the curve was fit by a Langmuir 1:1 stoichiometric model to obtain the dissociation constant using the Octet Analysis software.

For the blocking experiment, the RBD was grafted on the hydrated Ni-NTA biosensor, following which it was dipped in a well containing a mixture of (1 µl of sera, 4 µl of 1% BSA solution in PBS, and 195 µl of PBS to give a total volume of 200 µl). The biosensor was then dipped in PBS to remove non-specifically adsorbed antibodies. The association step was performed in ACE2 (0.025 mg/ml in PBS, 300s) followed by the dissociation phase in PBS.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors:

Correspondence should be addressed to:

*(D.A.) david.alsteens@uclouvain.be

*(A.B.P.) apoma@jppt.pan.pl

Author Contributions:

A.R. and D.A. conceived the project, planned the experiments, and analyzed the AFM and BLI data. A.R. and D.M. conducted the AFM experiments. A.R. and D.A. analyzed the AFM data. A.R. and R.N. performed the BLI and analyzed the data. and A.P. designed, performed and analyzed the SMD simulation. M.K. and R.N. helped with data AFM data analysis. J.S., Q.Z., S.P. offered useful suggestions. T.T.M.T. performed, and analyzed the MD simulation. A.B.P. designed and supervised the MD study. R.A.M.S. provided the starting structures of RBD variants. A.R., D.A., T.T.M.T., R.A.M., and A.P. wrote the paper. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Funding Sources:

This work was supported by the Université catholique de Louvain, the Foundation Louvain, and the Fonds National de la Recherche Scientifique (FRS-FNRS) under the Excellence of Science (EOS) programme (grant ID 40007527). This project received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant agreement No. 758224), from the FNRS-Welbio (Grant # CR-2019S-01). The funders had no role in study design, data collection, and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the paper. AR is an FSR incoming post-doctoral fellow of Université catholique de Louvain. D.A. and J.S is a research associate and post-doctoral researcher at the FNRS. A.B.P. acknowledges financial support from the National Science Center, Poland, under grant 2022/45/B/NZ1/02519. T.T.M.T acknowledges financial support by Vietnam National University, Ho Chi Minh City (VNU-HCM) under grant number C2020-18-19. Computational resources were supported by the PL-GRID infrastructure. Cartoons in Figs. 1b and 5a were created with BioRender.com.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests..

ABBREVIATIONS

AFM (atomic force microscopy), DFS (dynamic force spectroscopy), FD (force-distance), SMD (steered molecular dynamics), mAb (monoclonal antibody), BLI (bilayer interferometry).

REFERENCES

- (1) Wu, C.; Liu, Y.; Yang, Y.; Zhang, P.; Zhong, W.; Wang, Y.; Wang, Q.; Xu, Y.; Li, M.; Li, X.; Zheng, M.; Chen, L.; Li, H.; Wrapp, D.; Wang, N.; Corbett, K. S.; Goldsmith, J. A.; Hsieh, C. L.; Abiona, O.; Graham, B. S.; McLellan, J. S.; Yan, R.; Zhang, Y.; Li, Y.; Xia, L.; Guo, Y.; Zhou, Q.; Auerbach, A.; Brenk, R.; Schipani, A.; James, D.; Krasowski, A.; Gilbert, I. H.; Frearson, J.; Wyatt, P. G.; Shang, J.; Ye, G.; Shi, K.; Wan, Y.; Luo, C.; Aihara, H.; Geng, Q.; Auerbach, A.; Li, F.; Masaud Shah, Bilal Ahmad, Sangdun Choi, H. G. W.; Capuzzi, S. J.; Muratov, E. N.; Tropsha, A.; Utomo, R. Y.; Ikawati, M.; Meiyanto, E.; Khaerunnisa, S.; Kurniawan, H.; Awaluddin, R.; Suhartati, S.; Global, A.; Global, A.; Global, A.; Global, A. Structural Basis for the Recognition of SARS-CoV-2 by Full-Length Human ACE2. *Science (80-.)*. **2020**, *3* (3), 1–8.
- (2) Callaway, E. The Coronavirus Is Mutating - Does It Matter? *Nature* **2020**, *585* (7824), 174–177. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-02544-6>.
- (3) Ray, D.; Quijano, R. N.; Andricioaei, I. Point Mutations in SARS-CoV-2 Variants Induce Long-Range Dynamical Perturbations in Neutralizing Antibodies. *Chem. Sci.* **2022**, *13* (24), 7224–7239. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2sc00534d>.
- (4) Tao, K.; Tzou, P. L.; Nouhin, J.; Gupta, R. K.; de Oliveira, T.; Kosakovsky Pond, S. L.; Fera, D.; Shafer, R. W. The Biological and Clinical Significance of Emerging SARS-CoV-2 Variants. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* **2021**, *22* (12), 757–773. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41576-021-00408-x>.
- (5) Mccallum, M.; Czudnochowski, N.; Rosen, L. E.; Zepeda, S. K.; Bowen, J. E.; Walls, A. C.; Hauser, K.; Joshi, A.; Stewart, C.; Dillen, J. R.; Powell, A. E.; Croll, T. I.; Nix, J.; Virgin, H. W.; Corti, D. Evasion and Receptor Engagement. *Science (80-.)*. **2022**, *375* (February), 864–868.
- (6) Robbiani, D. F.; Gaebler, C.; Muecksch, F.; Lorenzi, J. C. C.; Wang, Z.; Cho, A.; Agudelo, M.; Barnes, C. O.; Gazumyan, A.; Finkin, S.; Hägglöf, T.; Oliveira, T. Y.; Viant, C.; Hurley, A.; Hoffmann, H. H.; Millard, K. G.; Kost, R. G.; Cipolla, M.; Gordon, K.;

- Bianchini, F.; Chen, S. T.; Ramos, V.; Patel, R.; Dizon, J.; Shimeliovich, I.; Mendoza, P.; Hartweger, H.; Nogueira, L.; Pack, M.; Horowitz, J.; Schmidt, F.; Weisblum, Y.; Michailidis, E.; Ashbrook, A. W.; Waltari, E.; Pak, J. E.; Huey-Tubman, K. E.; Koranda, N.; Hoffman, P. R.; West, A. P.; Rice, C. M.; Hatzioannou, T.; Bjorkman, P. J.; Bieniasz, P. D.; Caskey, M.; Nussenzweig, M. C. Convergent Antibody Responses to SARS-CoV-2 in Convalescent Individuals. *Nature* **2020**, *584* (7821), 437–442. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2456-9>.
- (7) Gharbharan, A.; Jordans, C. C. E.; GeurtsvanKessel, C.; den Hollander, J. G.; Karim, F.; Mollema, F. P. N.; Stalenhoef – Schukken, J. E.; Dofferhoff, A.; Ludwig, I.; Koster, A.; Hassing, R. J.; Bos, J. C.; van Pottelberge, G. R.; Vlasveld, I. N.; Ammerlaan, H. S. M.; van Leeuwen – Segarceanu, E. M.; Miedema, J.; van der Eerden, M.; Schrama, T. J.; Papageorgiou, G.; te Boekhorst, P.; Swaneveld, F. H.; Mueller, Y. M.; Schreurs, M. W. J.; van Kampen, J. J. A.; Rockx, B.; Okba, N. M. A.; Katsikis, P. D.; Koopmans, M. P. G.; Haagmans, B. L.; Rokx, C.; Rijnders, B. J. A. Effects of Potent Neutralizing Antibodies from Convalescent Plasma in Patients Hospitalized for Severe SARS-CoV-2 Infection. *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, *12* (1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-23469-2>.
- (8) Ozono, S.; Zhang, Y.; Ode, H.; Sano, K.; Tan, T. S.; Imai, K.; Miyoshi, K.; Kishigami, S.; Ueno, T.; Iwatani, Y.; Suzuki, T.; Tokunaga, K. SARS-CoV-2 D614G Spike Mutation Increases Entry Efficiency with Enhanced ACE2-Binding Affinity. *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, *12* (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-21118-2>.
- (9) Korber, B.; Fischer, W. M.; Gnanakaran, S.; Yoon, H.; Theiler, J.; Abfalterer, W.; Hengartner, N.; Giorgi, E. E.; Bhattacharya, T.; Foley, B.; Hastie, K. M.; Parker, M. D.; Partridge, D. G.; Evans, C. M.; Freeman, T. M.; de Silva, T. I.; Angyal, A.; Brown, R. L.; Carrilero, L.; Green, L. R.; Groves, D. C.; Johnson, K. J.; Keeley, A. J.; Lindsey, B. B.; Parsons, P. J.; Raza, M.; Rowland-Jones, S.; Smith, N.; Tucker, R. M.; Wang, D.; Wyles, M. D.; McDanal, C.; Perez, L. G.; Tang, H.; Moon-Walker, A.; Whelan, S. P.; LaBranche, C. C.; Saphire, E. O.; Montefiori, D. C. Tracking Changes in SARS-CoV-2 Spike: Evidence That D614G Increases Infectivity of the COVID-19 Virus. *Cell* **2020**, *182* (4),

812-827.e19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2020.06.043>.

- (10) Mansbach, R. A.; Chakraborty, S.; Nguyen, K.; Montefiori, D. C.; Korber, B.; Gnanakaran, S. The SARS-CoV-2 Spike Variant D614G Favors an Open Conformational State. *Sci. Adv.* **2021**, *7* (16), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abf3671>.
- (11) Gobeil, S. M. C.; Janowska, K.; McDowell, S.; Mansouri, K.; Parks, R.; Manne, K.; Stalls, V.; Kopp, M. F.; Henderson, R.; Edwards, R. J.; Haynes, B. F.; Acharya, P. D614G Mutation Alters SARS-CoV-2 Spike Conformation and Enhances Protease Cleavage at the S1/S2 Junction. *Cell Rep.* **2021**, *34* (2), 108630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2020.108630>.
- (12) Du, W.; Hurdiss, D. L.; Drabek, D.; Mykytyn, A. Z.; Kaiser, F. K.; González-Hernández, M.; Muñoz-Santos, D.; Lamers, M. M.; van Haperen, R.; Li, W.; Drulyte, I.; Wang, C.; Sola, I.; Armando, F.; Beythien, G.; Ciurkiewicz, M.; Baumgärtner, W.; Guilfoyle, K.; Smits, T.; van der Lee, J.; van Kuppeveld, F. J. M.; van Amerongen, G.; Haagmans, B. L.; Enjuanes, L.; Osterhaus, A. D. M. E.; Grosveld, F.; Bosch, B. J. An ACE2-Blocking Antibody Confers Broad Neutralization and Protection against Omicron and Other SARS-CoV-2 Variants of Concern. *Sci. Immunol.* **2022**, *7* (73), eabp9312. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciimmunol.abp9312>.
- (13) Ge, J.; Wang, R.; Ju, B.; Zhang, Q.; Sun, J.; Chen, P.; Zhang, S.; Tian, Y.; Shan, S.; Cheng, L.; Zhou, B.; Song, S.; Zhao, J.; Wang, H.; Shi, X.; Ding, Q.; Liu, L.; Zhao, J.; Zhang, Z.; Wang, X.; Zhang, L. Antibody Neutralization of SARS-CoV-2 through ACE2 Receptor Mimicry. *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, *12* (1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-20501-9>.
- (14) Wang, P.; Nair, M. S.; Liu, L.; Iketani, S.; Luo, Y.; Guo, Y.; Wang, M.; Yu, J.; Zhang, B.; Kwong, P. D.; Graham, B. S.; Mascola, J. R.; Chang, J. Y.; Yin, M. T.; Sobieszczyk, M.; Kyratsous, C. A.; Shapiro, L.; Sheng, Z.; Huang, Y. Antibody Resistance of SARS-CoV-2 Variants B.1.351 and B.1.1.7. *Nature* **2021**, *593* (May). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03398-2>.
- (15) Id, P. D.; Id, J. W. S.; Id, K. L.; Id, W. L.; Id, S. D.; Id, K. S. T.; Zhou, S.; Id, S. C.; Id, S.

- S. Cryo-Electron Microscopy Structures of the N501Y SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein in Complex with ACE2 and 2 Potent Neutralizing Antibodies. **2021**, 2, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3001237>.
- (16) Moulana, A.; Dupic, T.; Phillips, A. M.; Chang, J.; Nieves, S.; Roffler, A. A.; Greaney, A. J.; Starr, T. N.; Bloom, J. D.; Desai, M. M. Compensatory Epistasis Maintains ACE2 Affinity in SARS-CoV-2 Omicron BA.1. *bioRxiv* **2022**, No. September, 2022.06.17.496635. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-34506-z>.
- (17) Cerutti, G.; Guo, Y.; Liu, L.; Liu, L.; Zhang, Z.; Luo, Y.; Huang, Y.; Wang, H. H.; Ho, D. D.; Sheng, Z.; Shapiro, L. Cryo-EM Structure of the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron Spike. *Cell Rep.* **2022**, 38 (9), 110428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2022.110428>.
- (18) Yang, J.; Petitjean, S. J. L.; Koehler, M.; Zhang, Q.; Dumitru, A. C.; Chen, W.; Derclaye, S.; Vincent, S. P.; Soumillion, P.; Alsteens, D. Molecular Interaction and Inhibition of SARS-CoV-2 Binding to the ACE2 Receptor. *Nat. Commun.* **2020**, 11 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-18319-6>.
- (19) Koehler, M.; Ray, A.; Moreira, R. A.; Juniku, B.; Poma, A. B.; Alsteens, D. Molecular Insights into Receptor Binding Energetics and Neutralization of SARS-CoV-2 Variants. *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, 12 (1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-27325-1>.
- (20) Bouchiat, C.; Wang, M. D.; Allemand, J. F.; Strick, T.; Block, S. M.; Croquette, V. Estimating the Persistence Length of a Worm-like Chain Molecule from Force-Extension Measurements. *Biophys. J.* **1999**, 76 (1 I), 409–413. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3495\(99\)77207-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3495(99)77207-3).
- (21) Evans, E. Energy Landscapes of Biomolecular Adhesion and Receptor Anchoring at Interfaces Explored with Dynamic Force Spectroscopy. *Faraday Discuss.* **1998**, No. 111, 1–16.
- (22) Hane, F. T.; Attwood, S. J.; Leonenko, Z. Comparison of Three Competing Dynamic Force Spectroscopy Models to Study Binding Forces of Amyloid- β (1-42). *Soft Matter*

- 2014**, *10* (12), 1924–1930. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3sm52257a>.
- (23) Rankl, C.; Kienberger, F.; Wildling, L.; Wruss, J.; Gruber, H. J.; Blaas, D.; Hinterdorfer, P. Multiple Receptors Involved in Human Rhinovirus Attachment to Live Cells. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **2008**, *105* (46), 17778–17783. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0806451105>.
- (24) Mahmood, M. I.; Poma, A. B.; Okazak, K. I. Optimizing Gō-MARTINI Coarse-Grained Model for F-BAR Protein on Lipid Membrane. *Front. Mol. Biosci.* **2021**, *8* (February), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmolb.2021.619381>.
- (25) Liu, Z.; Moreira, R. A.; Dujmović, A.; Liu, H.; Yang, B.; Poma, A. B.; Nash, M. A. Mapping Mechanostable Pulling Geometries of a Therapeutic Anticalin/CTLA-4 Protein Complex. *Nano Lett.* **2022**, *22* (1), 179–187. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.1c03584>.
- (26) Zhu, R.; Canena, D.; Sikora, M.; Klausberger, M.; Seferovic, H.; Mehdipour, A. R.; Hain, L.; Laurent, E.; Monteil, V.; Wirnsberger, G.; Wieneke, R.; Tampé, R.; Kienzl, N. F.; Mach, L.; Mirazimi, A.; Oh, Y. J.; Penninger, J. M.; Hummer, G. Force-Tuned Avidity of Spike Variant-ACE2 Interactions Viewed on the Single- Molecule Level. **2022**, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-35641-3>.
- (27) Wang, Z.; Muecksch, F.; Schaefer-Babajew, D.; Finkin, S.; Viant, C.; Gaebler, C.; Hoffmann, H. H.; Barnes, C. O.; Cipolla, M.; Ramos, V.; Oliveira, T. Y.; Cho, A.; Schmidt, F.; Da Silva, J.; Bednarski, E.; Aguado, L.; Yee, J.; Daga, M.; Turroja, M.; Millard, K. G.; Jankovic, M.; Gazumyan, A.; Zhao, Z.; Rice, C. M.; Bieniasz, P. D.; Caskey, M.; Hatzioannou, T.; Nussenzweig, M. C. Naturally Enhanced Neutralizing Breadth against SARS-CoV-2 One Year after Infection. *Nature* **2021**, *595* (7867), 426–431. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03696-9>.
- (28) Cao, Y.; Su, B.; Guo, X.; Sun, W.; Deng, Y.; Bao, L.; Zhu, Q.; Zhang, X.; Zheng, Y.; Geng, C.; Chai, X.; He, R.; Li, X.; Lv, Q.; Zhu, H.; Deng, W.; Xu, Y.; Wang, Y.; Qiao, L.; Tan, Y.; Song, L.; Wang, G.; Du, X.; Gao, N.; Liu, J.; Xiao, J.; Su, X. dong; Du, Z.; Feng, Y.; Qin, C.; Qin, C.; Jin, R.; Xie, X. S. Potent Neutralizing Antibodies against

- SARS-CoV-2 Identified by High-Throughput Single-Cell Sequencing of Convalescent Patients' B Cells. *Cell* **2020**, *182* (1), 73-84.e16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2020.05.025>.
- (29) Dzimianski, J. V.; Lorig-Roach, N.; O'Rourke, S. M.; Alexander, D. L.; Kimmey, J. M.; DuBois, R. M. Rapid and Sensitive Detection of SARS-CoV-2 Antibodies by Biolayer Interferometry. *Sci. Rep.* **2020**, *10* (1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78895-x>.
- (30) Id, J. K. B.; Id, M. W. V. D. Biolayer Interferometry for DNA-Protein Interactions. **2022**, 5–9. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0263322>.
- (31) da Costa, C. H. S.; de Freitas, C. A. B.; Alves, C. N.; Lameira, J. Assessment of Mutations on RBD in the Spike Protein of SARS-CoV-2 Alpha, Delta and Omicron Variants. *Sci. Rep.* **2022**, *12* (1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-12479-9>.
- (32) Mannar, D.; Saville, J. W.; Zhu, X.; Srivastava, S. S.; Berezuk, A. M.; Tuttle, K. S.; Marquez, A. C.; Sekirov, I.; Subramaniam, S. SARS-CoV-2 Omicron Variant: Antibody Evasion and Cryo-EM Structure of Spike Protein–ACE2 Complex. *Science (80-.)*. **2022**, *375* (6582), 760–764. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abn7760>.
- (33) Sauer, M. M.; Tortorici, M. A.; Park, Y. J.; Walls, A. C.; Homad, L.; Acton, O. J.; Bowen, J. E.; Wang, C.; Xiong, X.; de van der Schueren, W.; Quispe, J.; Hoffstrom, B. G.; Bosch, B. J.; McGuire, A. T.; Veessler, D. Structural Basis for Broad Coronavirus Neutralization. *Nat. Struct. Mol. Biol.* **2021**, *28* (6), 478–486. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41594-021-00596-4>.
- (34) Zhang, X.; Wu, S.; Wu, B.; Yang, Q.; Chen, A.; Li, Y.; Zhang, Y.; Pan, T.; Zhang, H.; He, X. SARS-CoV-2 Omicron Strain Exhibits Potent Capabilities for Immune Evasion and Viral Entrance. *Signal Transduct. Target. Ther.* **2021**, *6* (1), 10–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-021-00852-5>.
- (35) Jiang, S.; Zhang, X.; Yang, Y.; Hotez, P. J.; Du, L. Neutralizing Antibodies for the Treatment of COVID-19. *Nat. Biomed. Eng.* **2020**, *4* (12), 1134–1139.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41551-020-00660-2>.

- (36) Pettersen, E. F.; Goddard, T. D.; Huang, C. C.; Meng, E. C.; Couch, G. S.; Croll, T. I.; Morris, J. H.; Ferrin, T. E. UCSF ChimeraX: Structure Visualization for Researchers, Educators, and Developers. *Protein Sci.* **2021**, *30* (1), 70–82. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.3943>.
- (37) Huang, J.; Rauscher, S.; Nawrocki, G.; Ran, T.; Feig, M.; De Groot, B. L.; Grubmüller, H.; MacKerell, A. D. CHARMM36m: An Improved Force Field for Folded and Intrinsically Disordered Proteins. *Nat. Methods* **2016**, *14* (1), 71–73. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.4067>.
- (38) Qiang, J.; Habib, S. A Second-Order Stochastic Leap-Frog Algorithm for Langevin Simulation. **2000**, *1*, 11–13.
- (39) Hess, B.; Bekker, H.; Berendsen, H. J. C.; Fraaije, J. G. E. M. LINCS: A Linear Constraint Solver for Molecular Simulations. *J. Comput. Chem.* **1997**, *18* (12), 1463–1472. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-987X\(199709\)18:12<1463::AID-JCC4>3.0.CO;2-H](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-987X(199709)18:12<1463::AID-JCC4>3.0.CO;2-H).
- (40) Bussi, G.; Donadio, D.; Parrinello, M. Canonical Sampling through Velocity Rescaling. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2007**, *126* (1). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2408420>.
- (41) Parrinello, M.; Rahman, A. Polymorphic Transitions in Single Crystals: A New Molecular Dynamics Method. *J. Appl. Phys.* **1981**, *52* (12), 7182–7190. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.328693>.
- (42) Abraham, M. J.; Murtola, T.; Schulz, R.; Páll, S.; Smith, J. C.; Hess, B.; Lindah, E. Gromacs: High Performance Molecular Simulations through Multi-Level Parallelism from Laptops to Supercomputers. *SoftwareX* **2015**, *1–2*, 19–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2015.06.001>.
- (43) Binnig, G.; Quate, C. . Atomic Force Microscope. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **1986**, *56* (9), 5-1-5–9. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781420075250>.

- (44) Thu, T. T. M.; Li, M. S. Protein Aggregation Rate Depends on Mechanical Stability of Fibrillar Structure. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2022**, *157* (5). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0088689>.
- (45) Poma, A. B.; Thu, T. T. M.; Tri, L. T. M.; Nguyen, H. L.; Li, M. S. Nanomechanical Stability of A β Tetramers and Fibril-like Structures: Molecular Dynamics Simulations. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2021**, *125* (28), 7628–7637. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.1c02322>.
- (46) Vuong, Q. Van; Nguyen, T. T.; Li, M. S. A New Method for Navigating Optimal Direction for Pulling Ligand from Binding Pocket: Application to Ranking Binding Affinity by Steered Molecular Dynamics. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **2015**, *55* (12), 2731–2738. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jcim.5b00386>.
- (47) Heymann, B.; Grubmüller, H. AN02/DNP-Hapten Unbinding Forces Studied by Molecular Dynamics Atomic Force Microscopy Simulations. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **1999**, *303* (1–2), 1–9. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614\(99\)00183-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614(99)00183-9).
- (48) Chwastyk, M.; Bernaola, A. P.; Cieplak, M. Statistical Radii Associated with Amino Acids to Determine the Contact Map: Fixing the Structure of a Type i Cohesin Domain in the *Clostridium Thermocellum* Cellulosome. *Phys. Biol.* **2015**, *12* (4), 46002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1478-3975/12/4/046002>.
- (49) Koehler, M.; Petitjean, S. J. L.; Yang, J.; Aravamudhan, P.; Somoulay, X.; Lo Giudice, C.; Poncin, M. A.; Dumitru, A. C.; Dermody, T. S.; Alsteens, D. Reovirus Directly Engages Integrin to Recruit Clathrin for Entry into Host Cells. *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, *12* (1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-22380-0>.